

Developing a Taxonomy and Metadata Schema for 3D Assets in the OEXR Library

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About RECITE

Led by St. Cloud State University (SCSU), the Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies (RECITE) seeks to improve STEM technician education through the accelerated integration of cutting-edge extended reality technologies into technician classrooms.

The partners in the collaborative are:

- CA2VES (NSF ATE Center)
- CAST
- Clemson University
- EARTH (NSF ATE Center)
- Motlow State Community College (MSCC)
- Somerset Community College (SCC)

To learn more about the project, visit recitexr.org.

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Glossary of Key Terms

- **3D Asset** – A digital object, model, or environment with spatial properties designed for display in immersive or interactive media formats.
- **Alt Text (Alternative Text)** – Descriptive text that conveys the essential information of an image or 3D visual for screen reader users.
- **Animated Object** – A 3D asset that includes time-based movement or transformation, often used to show processes or sequences.
- **Asset Type** – The classification of a 3D resource by its structural format and intended interaction level (e.g., Static Model, Simulation).
- **CC Licenses (Creative Commons)** – A set of standardized, open-access copyright licenses allowing creators to specify permissions for reuse, sharing, and attribution.
- **COLLADA (.dae)** – An open XML-based format designed for exchanging digital assets between various graphics software applications. It can store a broad range of 3D data, including geometry, materials, lighting, and animation, making it a good option for collaborative workflows, though it can sometimes be less efficient than FBX or glTF for real-time use.
- **Discipline** – A defined subject domain or academic area used to categorize the content relevance of a 3D asset.
- **FBX (.fbx or Filmbox)** – Developed by Autodesk, FBX is an industry-standard format, especially in game development and animation pipelines. It is a versatile format that can store not just mesh data, but also animations (skeletal and blend shapes), scene hierarchy, cameras, lights, and more complex material setups. Its proprietary nature means full compatibility can sometimes be a challenge across different software, but it's very robust for transferring animated assets.
- **Formative Assessment** – A method of evaluating student learning during the instructional process to inform teaching adjustments.
- **glTF (.gltf / .glb)** – Known as the "JPEG of 3D," glTF (GL Transmission Format) is an open-standard, royalty-free format optimized for efficient transmission and loading of 3D models and scenes, particularly for web and real-time applications (like AR/VR). It supports PBR materials, animations, and scene hierarchies, and its binary version (.glb) bundles everything into a single file, making it very convenient. It's becoming increasingly popular due to its open nature and performance.
- **Guided Practice** – A pedagogical strategy where learners engage with a 3D asset following structured prompts or instructions.
- **Interactivity Level** – The degree to which users can manipulate, explore, or affect a 3D asset within an experience.
- **Licensing and Attribution** – Metadata fields that define usage rights, reuse permissions, and creator acknowledgment for a 3D asset.

- **LMS (Learning Management System)** – A software platform (e.g., Canvas, Moodle) used to deliver, track, and manage instructional content.
- **Metadata** – Structured information describing a 3D asset’s characteristics, purpose, and usage (e.g., title, format, discipline, pedagogical use).
- **NSF ATE** – The National Science Foundation’s Advanced Technological Education program, focused on two-year institutions and technician education.
- **OBJ (.obj - Wavefront Object)** – A simple, open 3D file format that represents geometry (vertices, faces) without animation. Frequently used for static models and archival purposes.
- **OBJ (.obj)** – A very common and widely supported 3D asset format, known for its simplicity. It primarily stores mesh geometry (vertices, faces, UVs) and can reference external material files (.mtl) for basic colors and textures. It's excellent for static models and cross-software compatibility, but it doesn't support animation or advanced material properties like PBR (Physically Based Rendering).
- **Open Educational Resources (OER)** – Teaching, learning, and research materials that are free of cost and access barriers and openly licensed for use, adaptation, and distribution.
- **Open Exploration** – A pedagogical use where learners freely navigate or manipulate a 3D asset without prescriptive guidance.
- **Pedagogical Use** – The intended instructional role or function of a resource within a teaching or learning context.
- **Platform Compatibility** – Technical capacity of a 3D asset to function within specific environments (e.g., WebXR, Unity, Unreal Engine). Often depends on supported file formats such as glTF, FBX, OBJ, USDZ, or STL.
- **Simulation Object** – An interactive 3D asset that mimics real-world behavior or systems for experiential learning.
- **Situated Scenario** – A pedagogical use category where learners engage with a 3D asset in a realistic, context-rich problem space.
- **Static 3D Model** – A non-interactive digital representation of an object, location, or structure used for visual reference or analysis.
- **STL (.stl - Stereolithography)** – This format is primarily used for 3D printing. It represents 3D models as a series of connected triangles (tessellated surface). STL files only contain geometry data and do not store color, texture, or material information, making them ideal for rapid prototyping and manufacturing.
- **Taxonomy** – A hierarchical classification system used to organize assets based on shared characteristics or categories.
- **Texture Mapping** – The application of surface textures to a 3D model to increase realism or instructional clarity. The resolution of these textures can vary widely,

typically ranging from 512x512 pixels for smaller details or less prominent objects, up to 4096x4096 (4K) pixels for high-fidelity assets like main characters or prominent environmental elements, with higher resolutions offering greater detail at the cost of increased memory usage.

- **USDZ (Universal Scene Description – Zip)** – A format developed by Apple for sharing 3D content on iOS and ARKit-compatible devices. Ideal for augmented reality use in Safari and mobile apps.
 - **Virtual Environment** – An immersive, often navigable 3D space that simulates physical or conceptual environments for learning.
 - **XR (Extended Reality)** – An umbrella term that includes virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR).
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Executive Summary

The rapid growth of extended reality (XR) in education has highlighted a critical gap in the discoverability and reuse of open educational 3D assets. The Open Educational Extended Reality (OEXR) Library, launched through the RECITE project and supported by the EDUCAUSE XR Community Group, addresses this challenge by aggregating and curating reusable 3D models for educational use. This white paper outlines the development of a taxonomy and metadata schema for cataloging 3D assets in the OEXR Library, aimed at improving organization, pedagogical relevance, and interoperability.

With over 100 assets collected to date and a growing network of contributors across multiple institutions, the OEXR Library provides an evolving infrastructure to support immersive pedagogy. The taxonomy described here offers structured ways to classify assets by discipline, pedagogical function, technical specification, and more, while the metadata schema supports discoverability, reuse, and eventual integration with learning management systems (LMSs) and XR platforms. This work is intended to serve educators and researchers seeking to leverage open XR resources in teaching, learning, and scholarship.

Key outcomes of this work include:

- A proposed taxonomy for educational 3D assets and implementation with discipline-aligned structure
- A metadata schema based on common standards, customized for immersive content
- A roadmap for future development, including platform integration and accessibility tagging

This white paper forms the basis of a future peer-reviewed publication documenting the design, implementation, and scaling of the OEXR metadata system.

Introduction

Extended reality (XR) technologies, including virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), and mixed reality (MR), have increasingly gained traction as tools for immersive learning. Numerous studies have shown that XR can enhance learner engagement, spatial understanding, and content retention when applied effectively in educational contexts. However, the educational impact of XR depends on hardware and platforms as well as the availability of well-designed, pedagogically aligned content.

Three-dimensional (3D) asset models, simulations, and environments serve as the building blocks of XR experiences. Yet, in the current educational landscape, reusable open 3D content is fragmented, inconsistently tagged, and often difficult to discover. Educators who wish to integrate XR into their courses frequently encounter barriers in locating high-quality, curriculum-aligned models, especially when searching across commercial platforms or open repositories not optimized for educational use. This aligns with research showing that taxonomy-driven structuring of VR/AR content enhances both discoverability and reusability in educational contexts (Motejlek & Alpay, 2021).

The Open Educational Extended Reality (OEXR) Library is a community-driven initiative designed to make high-quality, openly licensed 3D models accessible to educators and researchers. A core component of the project is the development of a taxonomy and metadata schema to support asset discoverability, pedagogical alignment, and technical integration across XR platforms.

The challenge we address is clear: Without a shared structure for organizing XR content, educational institutions risk duplicating efforts, misaligning pedagogical needs, or underutilizing existing assets. This white paper presents a scalable, standards-aware framework to help remedy that challenge.

Project Context

The OEXR taxonomy and metadata schema originated within the RECITE (Resource Collaborative for Immersive Technologies) project, launched in October 2023 through the National Science Foundation (NSF) Advanced Technological Education (ATE) program (DUE #2331451-2331455). Funded as a collaborative initiative focused on improving access to open XR content for education, RECITE laid the groundwork for asset collection, contributor engagement, and initial metadata practices. The project quickly attracted interest from educators, instructional designers, and technologists seeking ways to bring immersive learning into formal curricula.

Recognizing the need for broader adoption and community support, the RECITE team partnered with the EDUCAUSE XR Community Group, an international network of educators and researchers working to expand XR capacity in higher education. This collaboration significantly expanded the scale and scope of the OEXR Library initiative, shifting from a small pilot to a shared infrastructure model.

Initially, asset contributors were asked to complete a standardized spreadsheet when submitting models to the OEXR Library. This pragmatic, low-barrier approach provided early insight into the types of metadata educators considered important: licensing, pedagogical alignment, file format, technical specifications, and source attribution. The structure of that spreadsheet informed the core fields of the metadata schema described in this paper.

To date, assets have come from multiple institutions, including university makerspaces, faculty-led XR projects, NSF-funded projects, and independent creators. The OEXR effort remains grounded in the belief that content reusability depends on well-defined classification systems that are both pedagogically meaningful and technically robust.

For a summary of this collaboration and its broader vision, see the EDUCAUSE article: <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2024/10/the-oexr-library-a-collaborative-approach-to-extended-reality-in-education>

Related Work and Metadata Standards

The design of the OEXR metadata schema draws on multiple existing frameworks for learning object metadata, digital asset management, and 3D content classification. While several established standards offer valuable guidance, few are fully equipped to address the pedagogical, technical, and experiential dimensions of immersive learning resources.

Key references include (DCMI, 2023; LRMI, 2022; Schema.org, 2023; IEEE, 2002; ISO, 2011; W3C, 2021; Sketchfab, 2024; CGTrader, 2024; Blender Market, 2024):

- **Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI):** A widely adopted, general-purpose metadata standard that provides a core set of descriptive elements (e.g., Title, Creator, Subject, Format). While DCMI is broadly applicable, it lacks specificity for educational or 3D/XR contexts.
- **Learning Resource Metadata Initiative (LRMI):** An extension of Schema.org tailored for learning resources. LRMI introduces fields such as `educationalAlignment`, `learningResourceType`, and `typicalAgeRange`, which offer partial support for educational metadata. However, LRMI does not include robust descriptors for 3D-specific characteristics (e.g., spatial interactivity, physics engines) or immersive

environments. The OEXR team recognizes the potential to propose custom extensions to LRMI vocabulary to better support XR content discoverability.

- **Schema.org:** A general-purpose vocabulary used to enhance web search and content indexing. While Schema.org includes entities like **MediaObject**, **LearningResource**, and **CreativeWork**, these lack formal educational ontologies or standardized properties for XR deployment. In the future, OEXR assets may incorporate Schema.org markup for search engine optimization and cross-platform metadata interoperability.
- **IEEE LOM (Learning Object Metadata):** One of the earliest standards to formalize educational metadata structure. While LOM is comprehensive, its adoption has waned due to complexity and limited alignment with web-native or immersive technologies. Nonetheless, it informed foundational concepts like learning context, aggregation levels, and pedagogical purpose.
- **ISO/IEC 19788 (Metadata for Learning Resources):** An international metadata framework compatible with LOM and SCORM. It aims to promote consistent descriptors for learning resources across systems. While it offers strong support for multilingual descriptors and learning outcomes, it lacks implementation guidance for XR-specific use cases.
- **Commercial and Community 3D Asset Platforms:** Popular marketplaces and community hubs such as **Sketchfab**, **CGTrader**, and **Blender Market** provide extensive libraries of 3D models. These platforms are well-suited for creators, developers, and artists, with robust visual tagging and model previews. However, they primarily emphasize commercial licensing and creative utility over educational metadata. For example, while Sketchfab supports technical tags and limited licensing indicators, it lacks structured fields for instructional level, pedagogical use, or curricular alignment. CGTrader and Blender Market also prioritize search by format, polygon count, and use case (e.g., game development), but do not offer educational filters. These platforms demonstrate the value of rich visual discovery but also highlight the gap in metadata that supports teaching, learning, and curriculum design.

In parallel with these technical standards, accessibility metadata is also an emerging area of relevance. W3C's **Accessibility Metadata guidance** and Schema.org's **accessibilityFeature** fields provide a starting point for tagging content with features such as alt text, tactile feedback, captions, or sign language support. While adoption is inconsistent across platforms, OEXR plans to incorporate accessibility tagging into future schema revisions to promote inclusive design.

The following table provides a comparative overview of existing metadata standards and platforms referenced above. It highlights their relevance to educational metadata, support for XR, accessibility tagging, and pedagogical application:

Standard / Platform	Education-Specific Metadata	3D/XR Compatibility	Accessibility Fields	Open Licensing	Supports Pedagogical Use
DCMI (Dublin Core)	Low	Format only	Optional	Yes	No
LRMI	Moderate	Limited	Partial (accessibilityFeature)	Yes	Partial
Schema.org	Moderate	Limited	Yes (accessibilityFeature)	Yes	Partial
IEEE LOM	High (legacy model)	No	Limited	Variable	Yes
ISO/IEC 19788	High	No	Limited	Variable	Yes
Sketchfab	No	Yes	No	Some	No
CGTrader	No	Yes	No	Some	No
Blender Market	No	Yes	No	Some	No
OEXR Schema (in development)	Yes	Yes	Planned	Yes	Yes

In summary, the OEXR schema is positioned as a **domain-specific, educator-informed extension** of general metadata principles, focused on the pedagogical, technical, and experiential dimensions of open XR assets for education. Full source details for the standards and platforms discussed are available in Appendix C: References.

OEXR Taxonomy Framework

The OEXR taxonomy and metadata schema are grounded in semantic web and XR design principles, alongside education-specific metadata standards. They serve two interdependent functions: the **taxonomy** provides a hierarchical classification of 3D learning assets based on subject domain, educational use, and asset type; the **metadata schema** defines a structured set of fields to describe each asset's attributes for search, filtering, and instructional alignment.

Taxonomy Design Principles

The taxonomy draws on established educational and workforce frameworks, including the NSF ATE program domains, STEM and liberal arts disciplines, and career-oriented classifications like Career and Technical Education (CTE) pathways. This structure ensures alignment with both academic and applied learning contexts. Each top-level category (e.g., Discipline, Pedagogical Use) is designed to be extensible, version-controlled, and adaptable as the OEXR Library grows.

The taxonomy is also grounded in practical classroom needs, shaped through input from instructional designers, community college faculty, informal educators, and technical specialists during the RECITE project. Particular attention was paid to ensuring the framework supports pedagogical relevance, platform interoperability, and accessibility.

Metadata Schema Overview

The metadata schema complements the taxonomy by offering descriptive fields that make assets searchable, sortable, and pedagogically meaningful. These fields are informed by Dublin Core, LRMI, and learning object metadata practices, but extend them to meet the specific needs of XR contexts.

Key field categories include:

- **Descriptive** (e.g., Title, Description, Creator)
- **Instructional** (e.g., Discipline, Educational Level, Pedagogical Use)
- **Technical** (e.g., Format, File Size, Platform Compatibility, Interactivity Level)
- **Rights and Access** (e.g., Licensing, Attribution)

New and emerging fields, such as Accessibility Features, Associated Curricular Materials, and Deployment Environment (AR, VR, MR, WebXR), are being piloted for broader adoption. Deployment-specific metadata such as polygon count, asset resolution, and runtime

optimization will become increasingly important as the library supports multi-platform experiences.

Evolution of the Framework

The taxonomy and schema are designed to be iterative and extensible. As feedback from users, platform partners, and educators accumulates, OEXR will continue to refine the schema, clarify field definitions, and expand controlled vocabularies. Future updates may incorporate:

- Texture libraries (e.g., tile-able materials for user-customized models)
- Editable/derivative assets with change tracking
- Metadata for interactivity depth and simulation fidelity
- Predefined profiles for LMS/LTI deployment

Asset Type Revisions

Based on community feedback, some refinements are under review. For example, the distinction between “Interactive Scene” and “Simulation Object” has been flagged as unclear. A revised category, such as “Interactive Asset”, may better encompass scenarios where learners engage dynamically with content. Clearer definitions and usage examples will help users select appropriate types.

Overall, the OEXR taxonomy framework is positioned as a scalable, standards-informed classification and metadata structure, designed to bridge pedagogical intent, technical deployment, and educational interoperability across the growing ecosystem of immersive learning content.

Metadata Schema

The metadata schema developed for the OEXR Library provides structured fields to describe the pedagogical, technical, and licensing attributes of each 3D asset. These fields were derived from community input and aligned with standards such as Dublin Core and LRMI, while extending into XR-specific territory. Plugin-based approaches for platforms like Moodle demonstrate the potential of semi-automated metadata tagging for 3D/XR learning objects using standards like IEEE-LOM and OAI-PMH (Psyrra & Mangina, 2023).

The schema is designed to support both manual entry (via spreadsheet or form) and potential integration with platform APIs.

Field	Required	Description
Title	Yes	Descriptive title of the asset. Should be clear and searchable.
Description	Yes	Concise summary of the asset's content, use, and educational purpose.
Creator	Yes	Name(s) of individual(s) or teams responsible for creating the asset.
Date Created	Yes	Original creation date of the asset. Useful for version control.
Discipline	Yes	Subject area or academic field the asset supports.
Rights	Yes	Licensing designation (e.g., CC BY 4.0, CC0). Includes attribution requirements.
Format	No	File type or 3D format (e.g., glTF, FBX, OBJ, USDZ).
Language	No	Language of instructional or interface text, if any.
Educational Level	No	Intended user level (e.g., K-12, Postsecondary, Professional).
File Size	No	File size in MB or KB. Can be helpful for bandwidth considerations.
Publisher	No	Entity responsible for making the asset available. May be an institution or platform.
Institution/Organization	No	Organizational affiliation of the creator or funding source.
Curricular Materials Attached	No	Boolean value. Indicates whether lesson plans, guides, or worksheets are included.
Keywords	No	Tags to aid in search and filtering. Encouraged to use controlled vocabulary.
File Name	No	Internal reference name of the uploaded asset. For admin and file management purposes.

Field	Required	Description
Link (Admin-entered)	No	Final storage or access link once asset is published. Added by administrators.

The schema is extensible and may include future fields for interactivity levels, accessibility features (e.g., alt text, haptic feedback), and platform compatibility (e.g., Unity, Unreal, WebXR).

Platform Integration and Future Directions

The OEXR taxonomy and metadata schema are designed for broad interoperability, yet their success depends on integration with real-world platforms, particularly learning management systems (LMS), content management systems (CMS), and XR delivery environments. Successful implementation requires coordinated metadata and taxonomy architecture, as emphasized in digital asset management best practices (Hedden, 2018).

Users may encounter both technical and institutional challenges, including:

- **File Format Compatibility:** Not all platforms support the same 3D formats (e.g., glTF, FBX, OBJ). Some assets may need conversion or embedded viewers.
- **Viewer Limitations in LMSs:** Many LMSs (e.g., Canvas, Moodle, Blackboard) lack native support for XR content, often requiring third-party tools or LTI integrations.
- **Bandwidth and Storage Constraints:** Larger assets may impact users in bandwidth-limited contexts or institutions with cloud storage limitations.
- **Authentication and Access Control:** External assets may be blocked by institutional firewalls or require additional authentication layers.
- **Cross-Platform Behavior:** Assets can behave differently across web, mobile, and headset platforms, requiring consistent testing and QA.
- **Security and Privacy Compliance:** Some platforms have strict policies regarding third-party content and data privacy, especially in K–12 and medical fields.

To address these challenges and advance adoption, the OEXR initiative will:

- Pilot the taxonomy and metadata schema across diverse institutions.
- Collaborate with platform developers to support schema adoption and compatibility.
- Provide training and documentation for educators, instructional designers, and IT teams.
- Integrate accessibility and interactivity fields into future schema iterations.
- Encourage alignment with open standards such as WebXR and glTF.

- Gather and incorporate feedback from faculty, students, and technologists to refine and improve the framework.

Ultimately, the OEXR Library aims to empower a broad range of stakeholders – educators, technologists, designers, and learners – to build more inclusive, discoverable, and sustainable immersive learning ecosystems.

The OEXR Library taxonomy and metadata schema represent a critical foundation for structuring and scaling open educational 3D content in extended reality environments. By grounding the taxonomy in both academic and technical education frameworks and extending metadata practices to reflect XR-specific needs, this model supports improved discoverability, pedagogical relevance, and cross-platform reuse.

Looking ahead, the OEXR initiative will continue to:

- Pilot the taxonomy and metadata schema across diverse institutions.
- Solicit community feedback to refine and expand field definitions.
- Integrate accessibility and interactivity tagging in future versions.
- Collaborate with platform developers to support schema adoption in LMS, CMS, and XR authoring tools.

Ultimately, this framework aims to empower educators and technologists to build richer, more inclusive, and more sustainable XR learning ecosystems. Your feedback, contributions, and collaboration are welcome as this community-driven effort evolves.

Appendix A: Visual Taxonomy

OEXR Taxonomy

- | | | — IT Support & Networking
- | | | — Systems Administration
- | | — Arts and Humanities
- | | | — History
- | | | — Literature
- | | | — Philosophy
- | | | — Visual Arts & Design
- | | — Social and Behavioral Sciences
- | | | — Psychology
- | | | — Sociology
- | | | — Anthropology
- | | | — Political Science
- | | — Business and Economics
- | | | — Accounting
- | | | — Business Administration
- | | | — Marketing
- | | | — Economics
- | | — Education and Workforce Readiness
- | | | — Early Childhood Education
- | | | — K-12 Teacher Preparation
- | | | — Career and Technical Education (CTE)
- | | | — Workforce Development
- | | | — Apprenticeship & Industry Certifications
- | — **Asset Type**
- | | — Static 3D Model
- | | — Animated Object
- | | — Interactive Scene
- | | — Virtual Environment
- | | — Simulation Object
- | — **Pedagogical Use**
- | | — Content Demonstration
- | | — Guided Practice
- | | — Open Exploration

- | └─ Formative Assessment
 - | └─ Situated Scenario
 - | └─ **Technical Characteristics**
 - | └─ Format (e.g., glTF, FBX)
 - | └─ Level of Detail (Low, Medium, High)
 - | └─ Texture Mapping
 - | └─ Platform Compatibility (Unity, Unreal, WebXR)
 - | └─ **Licensing and Attribution**
 - └─ CC BY
 - └─ CC BY-SA
 - └─ CC0
 - └─ CC BY-NC
 - └─ CC BY-NC-SA
 - └─ CC BY-NC-ND
 - └─ CC BY-ND
 - └─ Institutional License
-

Appendix B: Sample Metadata Entry

Sample Metadata Entry 1: Human Heart Cross-Section Model

Title: Human Heart Cross-Section Model

Description: A detailed static model of a human heart cross-section used to illustrate blood flow and valve operation for high school biology. Optimized for desktop VR and WebXR environments.

Creator: Dr. Angela Gomez, Open Health Lab

Date Created: 2024-01-15

Discipline: Health Sciences > Anatomy and Physiology

Rights: CC BY 4.0

Format: glTF

Language: English

Educational Level: K–12, High School

File Size: 18.4 MB

Publisher: Open Health Lab

Institution/Organization: State University of Health Sciences

Curricular Materials Attached: Yes (includes worksheet and quiz)

Keywords: anatomy, circulation, heart, VR biology, science education

File Name: human_heart_cross_section_v1.glb

Link: [To be populated by admin]

Sample Metadata Entry 2: Interactive Physics Simulation

Title: Newton's Cradle – Force and Momentum Explorer

Description: An interactive simulation demonstrating Newton's third law through a virtual cradle. Learners can manipulate force inputs and observe momentum transfer in slow motion.

Creator: Prof. Michael Leung, OpenSim Lab

Date Created: 2023-06-10

Discipline: STEM > Physics

Rights: CC BY-SA 4.0

Format: glTF

Language: English

Educational Level: Postsecondary, High School

File Size: 12.2 MB

Platform Compatibility: WebXR, Unity

Associated Curricular Materials: Yes (includes lab activity and discussion guide)

Keywords: motion, force, physics simulation, energy transfer, Newton's laws

Interactivity Level: High

Deployment Environment: WebXR

Polygon Count: Medium

Accessibility Features: Captions, keyboard navigation

File Name: newtons_cradle_interactive.glb

Sample Metadata Entry 3: Virtual Environment for History

Title: Walkable Ancient Agora – Athens 430 BCE

Description: A historically accurate virtual reconstruction of the Athenian agora. Students can explore buildings, artifacts, and civic spaces with embedded voiceover narration.

Creator: Dr. Lena Markos, Immersive Humanities Initiative

Date Created: 2022-11-04

Discipline: Arts and Humanities > History

Rights: CC BY-NC-ND 4.0

Format: FBX

Language: English

Educational Level: Undergraduate

File Size: 85 MB

Platform Compatibility: Unreal Engine, Desktop VR

Associated Curricular Materials: No

Keywords: ancient history, Greece, Athens, virtual reconstruction, civic space

Interactivity Level: Low (exploratory navigation)

Deployment Environment: VR headset (HTC Vive, Oculus)

Polygon Count: High

Accessibility Features: Audio narration, colorblind-safe palette

File Name: agora_vr_walkthrough.fbx

Sample Metadata Entry 4: Standalone Tile-able Texture Pack

Title: Ceramic and Brick Texture Set – Tile-able (PBR)

Description: A set of four photorealistic, tile-able texture maps (diffuse, normal, specular, AO) suitable for surface detailing in historical or architectural 3D scenes.

Creator: RECITE Project Team

Date Created: 2024-02-27

Discipline: Cross-disciplinary (Engineering, Design, History)

Rights: CC0 (Public Domain)

Format: PNG + JSON (material config)

Language: N/A

Educational Level: All levels

File Size: 9.7 MB (total)

Platform Compatibility: Unity, Blender, WebXR-compatible renderers

Associated Curricular Materials: No

Keywords: PBR, textures, brick, ceramic, tile-able, materials

Interactivity Level: N/A

Deployment Environment: Universal

Polygon Count: N/A

Accessibility Features: Not applicable

File Name: ceramic_brick_textures_v2.zip

Appendix C: References

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Appendix D: Example Use Scenarios

Scenario 1: Technical Instructor – Advanced Manufacturing

A community college faculty member teaching “CNC Machining and Toolpath Simulation” searches the OEXR Library for:

- **Discipline:** Advanced Technological Fields > Advanced Manufacturing
- **Asset Type:** Simulation Object
- **Pedagogical Use:** Guided Practice
- **Format:** glTF Result: Locates a multi-part interactive simulation of a milling machine for use in a WebXR lab module.

Scenario 2: Health Sciences Faculty – Anatomy Lab Replacement

An instructor in an allied health program needs a virtual alternative to physical anatomy models. They search for:

- **Discipline:** Health Sciences > Anatomy and Physiology
- **Educational Level:** Postsecondary
- **Asset Type:** Static 3D Model
- **Accessibility Features:** Alt text, Haptic Support (future metadata field) Result: Finds multiple labeled anatomical models suitable for VR exploration and formative assessments.

Scenario 3: Dual Enrollment Coordinator – CTE Pathways

A high school CTE coordinator designs a dual enrollment program with the local technical college. They browse:

- **Discipline:** Career and Technical Education
- **Pedagogical Use:** Content Demonstration, Open Exploration
- **Curricular Materials Attached:** Yes Result: Curates an XR asset bundle for student career exploration in welding, HVAC, and IT networking.

Scenario 4: Instructional Designer – Undergraduate Biology Course

An instructional designer working on a general education biology course is looking for assets to complement textbook readings. They search for:

- **Discipline:** STEM > Biology
- **Asset Type:** Static 3D Model

- **Pedagogical Use:** Content Demonstration
- **Curricular Materials Attached:** Yes
Result: Selects 3D models of plant cells, mitochondria, and DNA structure to embed in LMS-based learning modules with guiding questions.

Scenario 5: High School Science Teacher – Interactive Earth Science Lesson

A high school teacher preparing a unit on plate tectonics and volcanism needs interactive visualizations for the classroom. They search:

- **Discipline:** STEM > Earth & Environmental Sciences
- **Asset Type:** Interactive Scene
- **Educational Level:** K–12, High School
Result: Finds an immersive 3D model of the Ring of Fire, allowing students to explore tectonic plate boundaries and active volcano sites in VR.

Scenario 6: Informal Educator – Museum-Based Learning Experience

An exhibit designer at a natural history museum is creating a mixed-reality experience for middle school field trips. They search for:

- **Discipline:** Arts and Humanities > History
- **Asset Type:** Virtual Environment
- **Pedagogical Use:** Open Exploration
Result: Identifies a walkable historical model of an ancient Roman street, allowing students to engage with culture and artifacts through guided VR tours.

These scenarios demonstrate how the OEXR taxonomy enables practical filtering, reuse, and alignment across varied instructional contexts.
